

Research Article

Assessment of Graduating Students Perception on Agricultural production: Case study of Federal Colleges of Agriculture in Oyo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined Perception of the Graduating Students of Federal Colleges of Agriculture in Oyo State to participate in Agricultural production. Primary data were collected using a structured interview schedule to select 180 respondents in the study area using multi-stage sampling technique. Data collected were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics such. The result of the study indicated that more than half (52.8%) were females, 78.8% of the respondents were within the age range of 20-25years, a large percentage 64.4% of the respondents were from a household size of 2-5 people which is fair for the needed labour force for agricultural activities. 71.7% of the respondents reside in urban areas, Many (55.6%) of their parents were involved in non-farming activities. Close to a quarter (39.4%) of the respondents chose Animal production as their most preferred agricultural enterprise to venture into after graduation. Furthermore, the study showed that respondents had a positive perception that participating in agricultural production enhances household food security, creation of employment and enhances job security with the mean scores of 4.72, 4.44 and 4.42 respectively which was greater than the grand mean score 4.15. The majority of the respondents (82.8%) showed willingness to participate in Agriculture even if there is opportunity for a white collar job. The result of the Chi- square analysis showed that all the socioeconomic characteristics were not significant except sex. Agricultural policies that will help sustain the interest and

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motivate agricultural graduates to embrace farming as a career should be made.

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Introduction

Agriculture occupies a central position in Nigeria's economy, however its growth and productivity is still considered low inspite of adequate and available natural resources necessary for any economic development in terms of Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Nigeria, being an agrarian economy needs to expand the tentacles of Agriculture in order to boost productivity thereby presenting a growing economy. In the 1960s, agricultural sector serves as the main source of employment, income and foreign exchange earnings for Nigeria (Azih, 2011). Yet, unemployment is increasing at an alarming rate in an unbearable dimension in Nigeria from 13.9% in the third quarter of 2016 to 14.2% in the last quarter of the same year (National Bureau of Statistics, 2017), such that citizens are becoming frustrated, violent and aggressive as a result of joblessness thus resulting into an upward trend of criminal activities.

Agricultural production has potentials of combating the menace of unemployment in Nigeria if only youths and graduates of agriculture can explore the opportunities it possesses. The future of Nigeria lies in youth's participation in farming as agriculture itself aids creation of employment rather than the youths bothered with seeking employment (Edozien, 2004). Consequently, quite a handful of agricultural based institutions are all over the nation, presenting youths with opportunities for adequate training in all fields of Agriculture by the Nigerian Government so that youths' interest is stimulated to embrace farming as a career.

To this regard, several programmes have been developed to facilitate meaningful youth participation among which include Youth Empowerment Scheme (YES), National Youth Service Corps (NYSC), National Directorate of Employment (NDE) in addition to various vocational trainings so as to boost entrepreneurial action especially in the field of agriculture which are avenues for youth to build a career as a product of the vocational knowledge they have received to create job opportunities which is important for creating wealth (Hitt *et al.*, 2001). Choice of career in farming has a lot to do with the kind of skill and entrepreneurial knowledge that is acquired. Since youths are the backbone of the development of any country, there is every tendency for them to maximise an available opportunity to put the knowledge acquired to use so long they

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are technically strong and practically willing to venture into agricultural production (Saliu *et al.* , 2016).

Efforts have been made in training young people in the fields of Agriculture so as to build middleman power in most of the Colleges of Agriculture controlled by Government as advocated that education should produce graduates who can create rather than seek employment (Munowenyo, 1999). However, this has not achieved the anticipated results as these institutions have been training agricultural graduates yet they are not willing to participate in agriculture thus increasing skill and labour shortage that is still posing as a monster with food security a mirage in Nigeria. Thus, this study sought to assess the perception of graduating students on agricultural production.

Methodology

The study was conducted in the Federal Colleges of Agriculture and Animal Health and Production Technology Moor Plantation, Ibadan, the capital city of Oyo State, Nigeria. The colleges are located within Ibadan South West Local Government Area of Oyo State. The sample frame was made up of five (5) departments in the College of Agriculture namely; Departments of Horticulture, Post Harvest Management, Pest Management, Farm Power and Machinery, Crop Production Technology and three(3) departments from the College of Animal Health and Production Technology namely' Departments of Agricultural Extension and Management, Animal Health Technology and Animal Production Technology. Proportionate and random sampling techniques were used in selecting sixty percent of the graduating students from each of the departments making a total of one hundred and eighty respondents for the study. The sample size consists of both male and female students. A questionnaire was used to collect information on the willingness and socio- economic variables of the respondents. The data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics such as Table, frequency and percentage while inferential statics used was chi square analysis. Five point likert-scale was used to analyse perception. It was measured using Strongly Agreed (SA), Agree (A), Undecided (U), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) and assigned to 5,4,3,2 and 1 respectively for positive statements but reversed for negative statements. The mean for each statement was obtained while the grand mean for all the statements was also calculated. the means for the less than1.5, 1.6-2.5, 2.6-3.5,3.6-4.5 and 4.6 above were interpreted as SD,D,U,A and SA respectively. One hundred and eighty questionnaires were distributed and all of them were returned.

$$X = \sum fx (Ai) / N$$

Where X= mean score, fx = frequency Ai = value assigned to each respondent, N= sample design, \sum = summation

Data were subjected to both descriptive statistics (mean, frequency and percentage) and inferential statistics (Chi-square) using SPSS (v. 22). A Kendall's coefficient of concordance was done to ascertain the degree of agreement among the respondents on the statements related to their perceptions on agricultural production.

Results and Discussion

Table 1: Distribution of respondents by Personal characteristics (n=180)

Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age (years)		
20-25	131	78.8
26-30	47	26.1
31-37	2	1.1
Sex		
Male	85	47.2
Female	95	52.8
Religion		
Christian	142	78.9
Islam	38	21.1
Marital status		
Single	168	93.4
Married	12	6.7
Household size		
2 - 5	161	64.4
6 - 9	56	31.1
10 and above	8	4.4
Family location		
Urban area	129	71.7
Peri-urban center	24	13.3
Rural area	27	15
Parent occupation		
Farming activities	80	44.4
Non farming activities	100	55.6

Source : Field survey,2016

Table 1 shows the personal characteristics of the respondents. Results showed that about half (52.8%) and 47.2% were females and males, respectively, implying that there is about equal opportunity given to both male and female in the discipline of Agriculture so as to make a better livelihood. This result agrees with the fact that both sexes had the chance to be educated (Ayanda *et al.*, 2012). The majority of the respondents (78.8%) were within age range of 20 -25 years. This implies that almost all the respondents were young with the potential strength required to be productive and ready to face the risk in agricultural activities. This is in line with the work of Fadipe *et al.* (2014), who reported that most of the respondents (68.4%) still have high level of potential efficiency to participate in agriculture as long they are willing. Also, the majority of the respondents (93.3%), were unmarried with only a few (6.7%) were married, thus indicating that most of the students would want to wait till they graduate and earn a living before considering marriage as it may be a distraction for participating in Agricultural production. This also agrees the work of Saliu *et al.* (2016), who asserted that majority of the respondents, could still decide on making Agriculture their career since they were free from a spouse or children influence.

Table 2: Distribution of Respondents' Preference for Agricultural Enterprise

Agricultural Enterprise	Frequency	Percentage
Animal production	71	39.4%
Processing and storage	10	5.6%
Marketing	6	3.3%
Health Service (livestock)	20	11.1%
Extension Service	8	4.4%
Horticulture	10	5.6%
Fabrication	12	6.7%
Crop Production	43	23.9%

Source: Field survey, 2016.

The study further showed that the majority (71.7%) of the respondents resides in the urban areas, 13.3% in the peri-urban and 15% in the rural areas where agriculture seems to be a major source of livelihood. Contrarily, Adebo and Sekunmade (2013) reported that about 70% of the respondents lived in the rural areas. The result also shows that more than half (55.6%) of the respondents' parents were into non-farm activities while 44.4% of the respondents engaged in farming activities. This is expected as majority of the respondents reside in urban centres with few living in the rural. Therefore their

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means of livelihood cuts across various employment activities aside farming yet, they have preference for agricultural education as a means of creating employment stability (Saliu et al., 2016).

Table 2 revealed different Agricultural production enterprise respondents are interested in. Results showed that more than a quarter showing interest in livestock production (39.4%), followed by crop production (23.9%). This agrees with the work of Montshuwe (2008) who identified livestock farming as the major enterprise with the most likely chance of improving household food security and addressing poverty alleviation in the rural areas. However, respondents were not really interested in extension service delivery (4.4%), processing and storage (5.6%), marketing (3.3%), horticulture (5.6%), fabrication (6.7%) and health service delivery (11.1%). Responses could be viewed as not professionally adequate in itself and it could also be that respondents don't feel it's could be taken as a career unlike livestock and crop production.

Table 3: Distribution of Respondents based on their Perception on Agricultural Production

Perception statement	SA (%)	A (%)	U (%)	D (%)	SD (%)	Mean Rank
Participation in Agricultural production enhances household food security	130 (72.2)	49 (27.2)	1(0.6)	-	-	6.62
Job creation	120 (66.7)	57 (31.7)	3(1.7)	-	-	6.49
Capacity building	56(31.1)	86(47.8)	33(8.3)	5(2.8)	-	4.73
Sustainability	81(45)	90(50)	8(4.4)	1(0.6)	-	5.70
Job security	-	5(2.8)	14(7.8)	100(55.6)	61(33.9)	5.06
Income generation	3(1.7)	4(2.2)	3(1.7)	75(41.7)	95(52.8)	5.78
Diversification of livelihood	8(4.4)	6(3.3)	12(6.7)	63(35)	91(50.6)	5.54
It yields poor returns	17(9.4)	30(16.7)	26(14.4)	65(36.1)	42(23.3)	2.67
The start-up capital is high.	18(10)	43(23.9)	30(16.7)	57(31.7)	32(17.8)	2.41

Source: Field survey, 2016.

SA- Strongly Agree; A-Agree; U- Undecided; D - Disagree; SD-Strongly Disagree

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Table 3 shows the distribution of respondents based on their perception on agricultural production. Results showed that respondents perceived that participation in Agricultural production enhances household food security with the mean score of 4.71 which is well above the grand mean score of 4.15. This implies that majority of the respondents strongly agreed that practising Agriculture is panacea for food insecurity at household level. This agrees with the work of Botlhoko and Oladele (2013). Perception statement on “ participating in Agriculture enhances Job creation with a mean score of 4.62 and this indicated that respondents strongly agree that Agriculture is a major discipline that can be embraced if and only if a reduction in the rate of unemployment is to be guaranteed. Perception statement of participation enhances job security had a mean score of 4.42 indicating that the respondents strongly agreed with the statement. Also, Participating in agriculture is sustainable and a mean score of 4.38 indicating that the youth involvement in agriculture is an antidote for sustaining the nation’s economy.

This agrees with the findings of Saliu *et al.*, (2016) who opined that through government interventions, young people who pick interest in Agriculture finds it sustainable. Respondents viewed participating in agriculture as a means to generate income, diversify livelihood and enhances capacity building with the mean score of 4.24, 4.21 and 4.07 respectively. This finding agrees with the work of Adebayo and Sekunmade (2013), who opined that farming serve as a stepping stone to other profession. Thus, participating in Agriculture encourages in livelihood diversification. Also, Adeboye and Eniolorunda (2016) opined that incorporating youths into Agriculture will facilitate capacity building and empowerment.

Table 4. Test of degree of association among the rankings given by the respondents

Variables	Values
N	180
Kendall's W ^a	.410
Chi-Square	589.729
Df	8
Asymp. Sig.	.001

^aKendall's Coefficient of Concordance; df - degree of freedom , N- sample size

However, a mean score of 3.47 and 3.23 which is less than the grand mean score (4.15) represents the respondents’ perception of ‘participating in Agriculture leads to poor returns on investment and start up capital is high “which are negative statements as

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the students felt agriculture is not as profitable as having a white collar because of the low financial status farmers in the society especially those who work tirelessly with little or no evident improvement in their social status.

The Kendall's coefficient of concordance (W) was 0.41 with a calculated chi square value of 589.73, as shown in Table 4. Therefore, the null hypothesis of independence among rankings was rejected and it was inferred that the respondents did apply the same standard in ranking the statements related to their perceptions on agricultural production. It was also observed that among the statements rated, most highly and regarded as most important by all the respondents was that Participation in agricultural production enhances household food security (Table 4). The implication of this finding is that, as pointed out by Schipper *et al.* (2008), if it is not recognised that participation in Agricultural production enhances household food security, and then measures to participate will not be prioritized. Similar result was obtained by Abegunde *et al.*, (2017) in a study on climate change among farmers.

Table 5: Relationship between Personal characteristics and respondents' willingness to participate in agricultural production

Explanatory variables	χ^2	P-value	Df	Level of significance
Age	21.451	0.493	22	Not significant
Sex	5.837	0.044	2	Significant
Household size	1.770	0.616	4	Not significant
Family location	2.054	0.726	4	Not significant
Parents occupation	2.749	0.601	4	Not significant

Source: Field survey, 2016.

Table 5 shows the relationship between selected personal characteristics and respondents' willingness to participate in agricultural production. It was found that there were no significant relationships between age, household size, family location and parents' occupation and their willingness to participate in Agriculture. This implies that none of these have any effect on the willingness of the respondents' engagement in Agricultural production. However, sex had significant relationship with the willingness of the respondents to engage in Agriculture. This implies that both male and female graduates' of Agriculture are ready to farm without any form of restrictions or restrain. This is not in line with the work of Ibitoye (2010) who reported that there is a statistical preference for agriculture between male and female students or youths. Since there is a positive perception towards engaging in Agriculture after graduation, this may explain

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it, the reason for both male and female students to be willing to build a career in agriculture.

Conclusion

The study revealed that agricultural production is positively perceived to be a profession as it enhances household food security, job creation. Most of them have a preference for animal production as an agricultural enterprise than other aspects of agriculture. This would draw the attention of policy makers to place more emphasis and importance on livestock production so as to command the interest of many youths, especially graduates of Agriculture for their full participation in agricultural production. Furthermore, the study showed that almost all the respondents are ready and willing to take up practical agriculture as a means of creating jobs and reduce the rate of unemployment in the nation. The exposure and experience in agriculture through the formal educational system has increased their chance to be involved in agriculture after graduation.

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